

THE SECRETS OF PAINTING ARE IN MY EYES

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ANNOTATION: This article talks about the specific features of easel painting, the gradual development of easel painting in Uzbekistan, artists working in easel painting.

Key words: easel, painting, fine art, plastic, nature, artist.

As you know, the field of easel painting that I am studying takes a major place in visual arts as a major. Easel painting is one of the most common types of art in modern fine art.

Usually, such pictures are worked on cloth stretched on a specially made frame. Such paintings are also called easel paintings because they are made on a separate easel called an easel. If it is a work of easel, it is a product of free creativity and activity. One of the most convenient aspects of it is that we can put it where we want and display it.

Easel paintings, unlike monumental and decorative paintings, are not directly related to other types of art. Such paintings, in addition to reflecting important events and events, also have the ability to show a person's feelings, experiences, character and uniqueness. In addition, we can see the subtle changes that occur in nature, the beauty of nature, its diversity and its elegant aspects. It is more possible to show all of this to the public quickly by describing and vividly expressing it.

In the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20 th century, the period of visual art of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, began to take shape.

During this period, he showed his influence through representatives of Russian and other nations. In contrast to the working methods and laws specific to miniatures, this visual art developed in European countries on the basis of more advanced three-dimensional laws was almost non-existent in our country at that time. At this time, mainly, the representatives of art were more engaged in folk decorative art. It prepares to create works with a deep philosophical theme through easel painting, improves artistic taste, introduces fine art works. The importance of pencil drawing is important in paintings. The painting is based on the laws of the color structure of the real form. As artists, we define painting as "100 percent pencil drawing and 100 percent painting." The role of pen drawing in the attractive output of a painting is incomparable. However, a skilled artist can paint the work without using a pencil. In the process of research, the artist feels that the painting is directly related to the pencil drawing. That is, the spatial arrangement of objects, the accuracy of proportions, the correct placement of colors, and the completion of the work as a whole depend to a large extent on the creator.

When the artist has mastered the pencil drawing carefully, the intended goal of the painting can be achieved, otherwise, if we analyze the work of the poorly resolved pencil drawing, no matter how attractive the colors are, this work cannot be called high-quality. Therefore, the historical experiences of various art schools testify that perfect mastery of pen drawing in the early stages of education creates conditions for further processes.

Tintoretto, one of the representatives of the European Renaissance, said: "Painting!" . To be an artist To Fioletti's question about what additional advice you would give Tintoretto: "Painting and painting again!" — painting, believed that it gives elegance and perfection to the painting.

The great sculptor Michelangelo saw the root and foundation of any science in a pencil drawing. "The pen drawing is a pole and a compass that always guides us and is a factor of salvation for those who are drowning in the ocean of different colors,"

said Charles Lebrun. And Engr wrote the words of his song on the doors of his workshop - "I will teach pencil drawing to students who come here, and when they leave, they will become masters of painting." "There is such a thing, which is the basis of all types of art, and this is pencil drawing. "Whoever masters the art of pencil drawing, he can master both painting and sculpting," Karacchi said. The works of mature artists are remarkable for the skillful composition of the work, the topicality of the subject, and the harmony of warm and cold colors. In the painting, the presence of fine plastic form, proportionality, and spatial qualities play an important role. Painter is full of these aspects of nature It is only useful if it can reflect. You have these aspects otherwise, the image is of very careless, sloppy quality is considered work.

A number of effective works are being carried out by artists in the further development of visual art in Uzbekistan and taking its place in the world visual art. The creation of works of various genres created by artists and their participation in a number of international exhibitions is a clear proof of this. In addition, it is appropriate to highlight the work of several artists such as Z. Fakhritdinov, B. Jalolov, M. Nuritdinov, R. Kudaiberganov, J. Umarbekov, A. Nuriddinov, M. Toshmurodov, A. Ikromjonov, S. Rakhmetov. In their works, we can see the expression of the beauty and values of mother earth.

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